

Financial Constraints, Environmental Uncertainty, and Tax Aggressiveness: Descriptive Evidence from Indonesian Mineral and Coal Mining Firms

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 30 June 2026</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Umi Rahma Dhany</p>	<p>This study aims to describe earnings management, financial constraints, environmental uncertainty, audit quality, and tax aggressiveness in mineral and coal mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2019–2023 period. The study uses a descriptive quantitative approach with secondary data obtained from financial statements and annual reports. The research sample was determined using a purposive sampling technique, resulting in 19 companies with 95 observations after the data screening process. Analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics, including mean, median, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation values. The results show that the level of earnings management in mining companies is relatively low and homogeneous. Financial constraints have high variations, reflecting differences in funding capabilities and liquidity conditions between companies. Environmental uncertainty is at a moderate level with a relatively uniform pattern, indicating that most companies face similar business risks due to commodity price fluctuations and market dynamics. Tax aggressiveness shows significant variation between companies, while audit quality is relatively high, indicated by the dominant use of Public Accounting Firms affiliated with the Big Four. These findings provide an empirical overview of the characteristics of mining companies in facing funding pressures, environmental uncertainty, and managing tax obligations.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: earnings management, financial constraints, environmental uncertainty, audit quality, tax aggressiveness, mineral and coal mining companies.</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

Taxes are the primary source of revenue for the government to meet various state and community needs (Karakotsios et al., 2020). Taxes are used as a tool to address economic inequality, finance public spending, build and maintain infrastructure, and stabilize the economy (Casara et al., 2022; Galdi, 2023). In line with these functions, taxes play a crucial role in maintaining national stability and prosperity, as well as promoting a sustainable economy (Chen, 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic has also contributed to a decline in tax revenues in various countries (Țibulcă, 2021). Governments need to implement effective and efficient tax policies, including by reducing the complexity of tax regulations, increasing legal certainty, and encouraging voluntary taxpayer compliance (Saptono & Ayudia, 2021). Another potential measure is strengthening the fight against tax evasion through the use of tax havens

(Lénártová, 2020). The role of taxes can be optimized to maintain stability and encourage sustainable economic growth (Lagravinese et al., 2020; Oluwatobi et al., 2021).

Companies, as subjects of income tax, must pay taxes according to a percentage of their profits. Taxes can be considered a burden and can be detrimental to companies because they can reduce net profit. This situation can motivate companies to minimize taxes by engaging in tax aggressiveness to increase net profit after tax. Many companies use various aggressive tax avoidance techniques to reduce their tax burden (Bilicka et al., 2023; Wang, 2024). Tax avoidance has become a significant issue in the context of modern taxation among academics, practitioners, and governments, especially in the context of globalization and increasingly integrated economies (Cho, 2020; De Simone et al., 2023). One of these activities includes shifting profits to countries with lower tax rates and using various other tax

mechanisms that allow companies to avoid paying taxes that should be paid (Atadoga, 2024). This will result in significant losses for countries that enforce tax provisions and maintain their tax bases (Abdelfattah & Aboud, 2020). Various efforts have been made to address tax avoidance, such as the implementation of country-by-country reporting (Joshi et al., 2020) and international tax law reform (Zhang, 2023). However, challenges remain as companies continue to seek loopholes to reduce their tax burdens (Mappadang, 2021). Governments, academics, and practitioners need to collaborate more closely to develop effective tax policies to address aggressive tax avoidance practices (Godar, 2024).

One example of the phenomenon of tax aggressiveness carried out by companies in Indonesia is PT. Bentoel Internasional Investama. The Tax Justice Network stated that the tobacco company owned by British American Tobacco (BAT) has engaged in tax avoidance in Indonesia, which can impact the state's losses of US\$ 14 million per year. This practice is carried out by diverting some of its income out of Indonesia. First, by implementing an intra-company loan strategy that costs Indonesia US\$ 11 million per year. Second, the loss to the state comes from royalty tax payments of US\$ 1 million per year, corporate tax of US\$ 1.3 million per year, and IT cost tax of US\$ 0.4 million per year (Prima, 2019). The practice of tax avoidance, other than the Bentoel case, is by the mining sector company PT. Adaro Energy. Tbk., a large corporation engaged in the coal mining sector, diverted much of the profits from coal mined in Indonesia. The tax avoidance loophole in the transfer pricing practice was carried out by the company from 2009 to 2017. PT. Adaro sells its coal at a lower price to Coaltrade Service International, which then resells it at a higher price to other countries, resulting in less taxable income. Diverting more funds through tax havens can impact Indonesia's tax revenue by nearly US\$14 million annually (Kencana, 2019; Suwiknyo, 2019).

One of the sectors most frequently involved in tax evasion is the mining sector (Arizah et al., 2024). The phenomenon of mining companies exploiting tax avoidance loopholes remains a hot topic among the public, as Indonesia is one of the largest coal producers. The coal mining industry contributes significant economic value but generates very little tax revenue (Yuliawati, 2019). This suggests that many companies in the mineral and coal mining sector, particularly in Indonesia, are still engaging in tax aggressiveness in an effort to minimize their tax burden.

Referring to the problems above, the objective of this research is to describe earnings management, financial constraints, environmental uncertainty, audit quality, and tax aggressiveness in mineral and coal mining companies in Indonesia. This research is expected to provide theoretical, practical, and policy contributions. From a theoretical aspect, the research results are expected to enrich the

development of the literature on tax aggressiveness by presenting audit quality as a moderating variable, so that it can serve as a reference for further researchers in developing a more comprehensive research model that is relevant to the development of science in the fields of accounting, taxation, and corporate governance. From a practical aspect, this research is expected to serve as evaluation material for mineral and coal mining companies in improving the quality of financial reporting and tax compliance.

Furthermore, the research findings can provide investors with more in-depth information regarding the characteristics of companies with a tendency to engage in tax aggressiveness. This information can be used as a consideration in investment decision-making, particularly in assessing earnings quality, corporate risk levels, and the sustainability of mining company performance. From a policy perspective, this research is expected to provide input for the Financial Services Authority (OJK) in strengthening regulations related to financial reporting transparency, corporate governance, and audit quality in mining companies. For the Directorate General of Taxes (DGT), the results of this research can be used as a consideration in formulating risk-based audit tax oversight policies. Furthermore, for the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (KESDM), this research is expected to provide input in formulating more focused, accountable, and sustainable mining sector governance, while simultaneously encouraging increased corporate taxpayer compliance, thereby increasing the contribution of state revenues from the mineral and coal sector.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Agency theory explains the relationship between agent and principal behavior. One or more principals (owners) make an agreement with an agent (manager) to carry out several business management activities and decision-making authority on behalf of the agent (Jensen & Meckling, 1997). Agents do not always act in the best interests of the principal if both parties in the relationship are oriented towards maximizing utility.

Schipper (1989) defined earnings management as a deliberate intervention in the financial reporting process for external parties for personal gain. Earnings management is considered the use of judgment by managers in financial reporting and transaction structuring to alter financial statements, either to mislead some stakeholders about the company's economic performance or to influence contractual outcomes that depend on accounting numbers (Ghazali et al., 2015; Sharma et al., 2025; Strakova, 2021). This definition positions earnings management as a phenomenon that falls on a spectrum, from efficient contracting to opportunistic behavior that damages information quality (Mi, 2014; Sharma et al., 2025). EM

occurs when management uses judgment in financial reporting and transaction structuring to alter financial statements, thereby misleading users about the company's economic performance or influencing contractual outcomes that depend on reported accounting numbers (Healy & Wahlen, 1999).

Financial constraints theory explains how capital market imperfections cause external financing costs to be higher than internal financing, so that investment, financing, and tax decisions are heavily influenced by internal cash availability (Edwards et al., 2012; Fazzari et al., 1987a; Fazzari & Athey, 1987). Lee & Feldman (1994) consider financial constraints as costly events that influence a company's optimal capital structure. This framework explains that liquidity pressures can encourage managers to seek alternative funding sources, including through tax avoidance strategies that increase after-tax cash flow (Edwards et al., 2016). Capital market imperfections cause some companies to lack adequate access to external capital, making investment excessively sensitive to cash flow (Fazzari et al., 1987; SM Fazzari & Athey, 1987). This phenomenon is consistent with pecking order behavior, where companies prefer: (1) internal financing; (2) relatively safe debt; and (3) new equity as a last resort, because equity is most vulnerable to undervaluation problems and issuance costs (Fazzari et al., 1987; SM Fazzari & Athey, 1987; Rajan & Zingales, 1996).

Environmental uncertainty refers to a form of uncertainty, meaning it is difficult to accurately predict environmental changes (Miliken, 1987). Uncertainty is a crucial factor in an organizational environment because it can impact an organization's survival. Prolonged environmental mismatches will threaten a company's survival (Luo & Yu, 2016). Environmental uncertainty is often driven by intense competition and unpredictable factors such as technological advances (Kafetzopoulos et al., 2020).

Uncertainty can hinder development regarding an organization's external environment, internal conditions, and others (Priem et al., 2002). Uncertainty as a compound construct consists of three types: state, effect, and response uncertainty (Liu & Almor, 2016; Milliken, 1987; Shrivastava et al., 2016). State uncertainty is the inability to predict "what is/will happen" in the environment, for example, regulatory changes, demand dynamics, or technological leaps. Meanwhile, effect uncertainty is the inability to predict the impact of these changes on the organization, for example, how new regulations affect profitability or cost structure. Response uncertainty is uncertainty about the consequences of available response options, so that managers do not know which response is most appropriate and what the outcome will be. There are three types of uncertainty in the corporate environment:

uncertainty regarding the unpredictable state of the organization's environment, such as suppliers, competitors, consumers, government, shareholders, etc.; uncertainty regarding incomplete understanding of the interrelationships between elements in the environment, and uncertainty about environmental change (Miliken, 1987).

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Research Design

A research design is a systematically created conceptual structure that includes an overview of what the researcher will do as a guideline for conducting the research (Kothari, 2004). More specifically, a research design encompasses the selection of research methods, data collection techniques, data analysis techniques, and drawing conclusions.

3.2 Population and Sample

A population is a collection of objects with specific characteristics that can be used to draw conclusions (Chandrarin, 2021). The population used in this study was 81 Energy Companies in the Mineral and Coal Mining Sub-Sector listed on the IDX for the 2019-2023 period (5 years), resulting in a total population of 405 observations.

A sample is a subset of a group of subjects that represents a population (Chandrarin, 2021). The sampling method used was non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling technique. This method was used because the sampling process does not consider the element of chance (Sanusi, 2014). The sample companies in this study were companies in the mineral and coal mining sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2019-2023 period.

3.3 Types and Sources of Research Data.

This research uses quantitative research with hypothesis testing because it uses numerical calculations based on each variable's measurement attributes (Chandrarin, 2021). The data source used in this study is secondary data, consisting of financial reports from mining and mineral sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX).

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques.

The data analysis in this study used Descriptive Statistical Analysis. The information obtained from data collection and data presentation through the use of descriptive statistical analysis methods is used to determine the characteristics of the sample used and describe the variables in the study. Descriptive statistics describe the collected data as seen from the average, median, and standard deviation values, so that the obtained data set will be presented concisely and neatly and can provide core information from the existing data

set (Vulandari et al., 2021). Descriptive analysis is intended to provide a description of the data related to each variable used in the study.

4. RESULT

4.1 General description

Companies in the mineral and coal mining sector play a strategic role in Indonesia's economic constellation. This sector is a major contributor to state revenue, although its business operations are highly vulnerable to fluctuations in global commodity prices, government regulatory dynamics, and energy transition issues. This study focuses specifically on companies in the mineral and coal mining sub-sector officially listed and traded on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). Based on data collected during the observation period from 2019 to 2023, the study population includes 81 corporate entities.

The sampling process from the total population was conducted in a structured manner using a purposive sampling method. This method was chosen to filter and obtain a truly representative sample that met the needs of the research variable analysis. The researchers established three main criteria in the selection process. First, the company must be consistently listed on the IDX during the 2019-2023 observation period without experiencing any delisting. Second, the company is required to publish fully audited annual financial reports (annual reports and audited financial statements) during that time period. Third, the financial reports must provide comprehensive information and data related to all research variables, namely elements of earnings management, figures for calculating the financial constraint index, historical sales value to measure environmental uncertainty, the identity of the auditing firm (Audit Quality), and the amount of tax burden to calculate the level of tax aggressiveness.

The application of these three stringent criteria eliminated dozens of companies that did not meet the data requirements. The final screening results identified 22 companies that were proven to meet all the absolute requirements as research samples. Subsequent observations were conducted over five consecutive years (2019-2023) on these 22 companies. Therefore, the total number of observations (firm-years) used as the basis for calculations in this panel data regression analysis was 110 observation points.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables

Researchers conducted descriptive statistical analysis to comprehensively map the characteristics of the data. This stage examined the mean, median, maximum, minimum, and standard deviation of each variable. The primary goal was to understand the distribution patterns and variation of the data before researchers could proceed

with hypothesis testing using panel data regression models.

Before executing descriptive and regression analyses, researchers deemed it necessary to conduct data screening on all observations. This evaluation is crucial for detecting the presence of extreme fluctuations in data (outliers), which could potentially compromise the stability and accuracy of the regression model being constructed.

The initial population of this study included 22 mineral and coal mining companies consistently listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange throughout the 2019–2023 period. This selection resulted in 110 balanced panel observation points. However, the researcher's initial estimates indicated that the regression model had weak explanatory power. This was evidenced by the Adjusted R-Squared value of only 0.060272 and the Prob(F-statistic) value of 0.062371. This condition was exacerbated by several predictors and moderating variables that failed to reach the expected level of significance.

Based on these findings, researchers conducted an in-depth evaluation and identified several companies that were causing model instability due to excessively volatile data patterns. A summary comparison of model quality before and after the data filtering process is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Comparison of Models Before and After Data Filtering

Criteria	Before Screening	After Screening
Number of Companies	22	19
Number of Observations	110	95
Adjusted R-Squared	0.060272	0.531865
Prob(F-statistic)	0.062371	0.000000

Table 1 shows that the initial model still contains issues that can affect the quality of the estimation, primarily due to the presence of several observations with extreme values (outliers). Based on the identification results, there are three companies that are the main sources of bias in the model, namely PT Indika Energy Tbk., PT Medco Energi Internasional Tbk., and PT Sumber Global Energy Tbk. PT Indika Energy Tbk. showed a tax aggressiveness value that was far below the sample average during the observation period, namely -0.907778 in 2019, -0.586906 in 2021, -0.494450 in 2022, and -0.366511 in 2023. These values deviate significantly from the majority of sample companies, which are in the

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range of -0.2 to 0.4, resulting in an average tax aggressiveness of -0.462517.

Meanwhile, PT Medco Energi Internasional Tbk. showed very high fluctuations in tax aggressiveness with a value of -1.112909 in 2019, increasing sharply to 0.736170 in 2020, then decreasing drastically again to -0.811691 in 2021. These very extreme changes have the potential to disrupt the data homogeneity required in panel data analysis.

In addition, PT Sumber Global Energy Tbk. Exhibits a significantly higher level of environmental uncertainty compared to other companies in the sample, with values of 1.450258 in 2019, 1.104885 in 2020, 0.932939 in 2021, 1.042191 in 2022, and 0.724934 in 2023. These values are far above the range of the majority of samples, which generally ranges from 0.1 to 0.3. Furthermore, this company's earnings management variable also exhibits a relatively extreme value in 2019, at 0.034081, far exceeding the industry average of 0.000343. The presence of these extreme observations has

the potential to distort the model estimation results, requiring further handling to improve the validity and reliability of the analysis.

To maintain the solidity and reliability of the regression model estimates, the researchers made a decisive methodological decision to exclude these three companies from the research sample. This data cleaning step yielded impressive results. Model quality improved dramatically, as evidenced by an increase in the Adjusted R-Squared to 0.531865 and an improvement in the F-statistic probability value to 0.000000. In conclusion, the post-filtering model proved to be significantly more robust and representative in explaining the research phenomenon.

This sample reduction resulted in a final total of 19 companies with 95 solid observation points for the researchers to process. This final data served as the basis for calculating descriptive statistics, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive Analysis Results (N = 95)

Variables	Mean	Median	Max	Min	Standard Deviation
Earnings Management	0.00034	0.00022	0.01359	-0.00700	0.00281
Financial Limitations	-324,062	-0.9507	1,468,918	-8,394,033	1,268,916
Environmental Uncertainty	0.24196	0.17325	0.70699	0.05967	0.15007
Tax Aggressiveness	0.09727	0.21482	0.84486	-149,802	0.31440
Audit Quality	0.67368	100,000	100,000	0.00000	0.47135
Moderation	0.00034	0.00000	0.01359	-0.00700	0.00257
Moderation	-295,400	-0.9392	1,468,920	-8,394,000	1,274,960
Moderation	0.15896	0.13158	0.70699	0.00000	0.16589

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics that provide an overview of the characteristics of each research variable. The earnings management variable has an average value of 0.000343 with a standard deviation of 0.002810. The average value close to zero indicates that, in general, earnings management practices in the mining companies included in the research sample are relatively low. Furthermore, the small standard deviation value indicates that variations in earnings management practices between companies tend to be homogeneous. The financial constraints variable has an average value of -3.240616 with a standard deviation of 12.689162. The high standard deviation value compared to the average indicates a significant difference in the level of financial constraints between companies. This is also reflected in the very wide range of values, namely from a minimum of -83.940333 to a maximum of 14.689178, which indicates heterogeneity in the funding capacity and liquidity conditions of companies in the mining sector.

Furthermore, the environmental uncertainty variable has an average value of 0.241958 with a standard deviation

of 0.150070. The lower standard deviation value than the average indicates that the level of environmental uncertainty faced by the sample companies is relatively uniform. This finding indicates that although the mining sector is heavily influenced by commodity price fluctuations and global market dynamics, the companies in the sample face a relatively controlled level of business environmental volatility. For the tax aggressiveness variable, the average value is 0.097267 with a standard deviation of 0.314404. The standard deviation value is much larger than the average, indicating high variation in tax-aggressive behavior between companies. The relatively wide data range, from a minimum value of -1.498024 to a maximum of 0.844859, indicates that the tax management strategies implemented by mining companies are very diverse during the study period.

The audit quality variable is measured using a dummy variable, where a value of 1 is assigned to companies using the services of a Public Accounting Firm (KAP) affiliated with the Big Four and a value of 0 for companies audited by a non-Big Four KAP. The average value of 0.673684

indicates that approximately 67.37% of observations in this study use the services of auditors affiliated with the Big Four. This condition reflects the high demand for better audit quality in mining companies as part of the implementation of good corporate governance. Meanwhile, the interaction variable used to test the moderating effect of audit quality shows a distribution pattern that follows the characteristics of its constituent variables. The interaction variable between audit quality and financial constraints has a relatively higher level of variation compared to other interaction variables. This finding indicates that the role of audit quality in moderating the influence of financial constraints on tax aggressiveness varies across companies, which is likely influenced by the fundamental conditions, funding structure, and operational characteristics of each company.

5. DISCUSSION

Earnings management in this study is formed and measured through an accrual earnings management approach (Accrual Earnings Management) using the Modified Jones Model proxy. In line with its theoretical concept, earnings management reflects deliberate managerial intervention in the financial reporting process with the aim of obtaining personal gain or achieving certain reporting targets. The results of descriptive statistical testing indicate that earnings management practices in the sample companies have an average (mean) of 0.00034 with a standard deviation of 0.00281. This average figure, which almost touches the zero point and has a very small standard deviation, provides a description that, in general, the level of accrual earnings manipulation in mineral and coal mining companies in Indonesia is at a very low level, with a relatively homogeneous reporting pattern between entities.

Despite being at a low aggregate level, the dynamics and fluctuations in reporting tactics are still recorded in certain entities. The data range, which ranges from a minimum value of -0.00700 to a maximum of 0.01359, describes the adjustment of accrual strategies by management in response to the company's internal conditions. Observations of data movements show that the highest level of earnings management was recorded by PT Indo Tambangraya Megah Tbk. in 2019, with a positive figure of 0.01358. Achieving this extreme positive value represents the practice of increasing income (income maximization), a pattern commonly executed when management is trying to meet profit expectations from the capital market, prevent debt contract violations, or protect their financial compensation.

Conversely, descriptions of income minimization practices are also clearly depicted in several companies. This is evident in data from PT Bumi Resources Tbk., which recorded negative earnings management of -0.00130 in 2020, and PT Adaro Energy Indonesia Tbk., which recorded

a negative earnings management of -0.00173 in 2019. This pattern of commercial profit minimization is generally implemented by management at peak profitability to avoid excessive political scrutiny from regulators, or as a cash-strapped maneuver when the company is restructuring its operations.

Overall, the low tendency for earnings management in the extractives sector reflects strong governance and the mining industry's high public visibility. Business entities managing strategic natural resources have a very high level of political exposure and are subject to multiple layers of oversight by stock exchange, tax, and environmental authorities. This restrictive ecosystem effectively limits managers' opportunistic maneuvering, as proposed by Agency Theory. Consequently, rather than resorting to extreme manipulation, mining company directors prefer to maintain performance stability through income smoothing practices to create a perception of long-term financial reliability in the eyes of stakeholders.'

5.1 Financial Limitations

Financial constraints in this study describe conditions in which a company experiences limited access to the funds needed to finance operational continuity and achieve its investment goals. The measurement of the financial constraints variable (X2) is represented by the Whited-Wu Index (WW Index) proxy, which comprehensively takes into account the level of cash flow to total assets, dividend payments, long-term debt structure, company size, and sales growth. Based on the results of descriptive statistical analysis, this variable recorded an average value of -3.24062 with a standard deviation level that jumped very high to reach 12.68916.

The high standard deviation, which far exceeds the average, illustrates the extreme variation and wide gap in liquidity resilience across entities in the mineral and coal mining sector. The reality of this highly fluctuating funding capacity range is clearly captured in the distribution of raw observation data for the sample companies. As a representation of this extreme condition, PT Elnusa Tbk. recorded the highest level of financial constraints (maximum value) of 14.68918 in 2021, indicating severe funding pressure, before the value plummeted to its lowest point (minimum value) of -83.94033 in 2022. On the other hand, a much more stable capital structure profile amidst market dynamics is demonstrated by large-scale issuers such as PT Adaro Energy Indonesia Tbk., which consistently maintained its financial constraint index within a narrow range, between -1.03609 and -1.13035 throughout the five-year observation period.

The extreme fluctuations and variations in the financial constraints index among these issuers are a direct reflection of the highly capital-intensive

operational anatomy of the extractive industry. The upstream mining chain, from exploration and procurement and investment in heavy equipment, land expansion, to the obligation to provide post-mining reclamation reserve funds, demands massive internal cash flow. This empirical description of field data aligns with the basic postulates of Pecking Order Theory and Financial Constraints Theory. Imperfect capital market mechanisms consistently trigger external financing costs that are significantly higher when compared to the use of internal company funds.

Therefore, when medium-sized mining companies or those experiencing declining performance are faced with tightening bank credit, they will struggle to fund projects at fair value, which in turn triggers an underinvestment problem. This descriptive statistical overview ultimately confirms that company management is constantly under pressure to maintain its going concern status. The varying levels of funding difficulties (ranging from default and insolvency to the threat of bankruptcy) underlie the differences in managers' resilience and motivation in seeking alternative liquidity sources to secure the company's operating cash flow.

5.2 Environmental Uncertainty

Environmental uncertainty in this study describes the level of operational volatility or turmoil faced by companies, which is represented through fluctuations in sales value due to macro market uncertainty and global commodity prices. The results of descriptive statistical analysis show that the environmental uncertainty variable (X3) recorded an average value of 0.24196 with a standard deviation of 0.15007. The fact that the standard deviation value is lower than the average provides a very clear empirical picture. This illustrates that although the mining industry is known to be full of turmoil, the level of business environmental volatility experienced by each sample company is basically still relatively homogeneous, similar, and evenly distributed across the industry.

The data range formed by these variable stretches from the most stable point at a minimum value of 0.05967 to the most volatile point at a maximum value of 0.70699. The dynamics of field data movements show that the highest escalation of environmental uncertainty (maximum value) was recorded by PT Harum Energy Tbk. in 2022. During the same year, extreme spikes in environmental uncertainty also simultaneously hit other issuers, as recorded in data from PT Bayan Resources Tbk., which jumped sharply to 0.53551, and PT Golden Eagle Energy Tbk., which reached 0.62640.

The pattern of simultaneous spikes in certain years clearly illustrates how global fundamental and macroeconomic conditions directly impact the sales stability of extractive corporations. This shock is a direct

reflection of the global energy crisis caused by geopolitical dynamics, sharp fluctuations in global mineral and coal benchmark prices, post-pandemic supply chain disruptions, and the dynamics of changing government regulations regarding domestic supply obligations (Domestic Market Obligations). These various external factors cumulatively create state uncertainty, making it difficult for companies to accurately predict market movements.

Despite facing very high market risk exposure, this data profile overall illustrates that volatility has become an inherent characteristic or a normal systemic risk in the Indonesian mining sector. The uniformity of data distribution and the absence of excessively wide variations between entities demonstrate that large-scale mining companies are generally accustomed to living and operating within the commodity supercycle. This description suggests that company management has assessed this uncertainty as part of daily operations and has generally fortified itself with various commercial risk management instruments, such as hedging contracts or long-term supply agreements, to ensure that such volatility remains within the company's controllable range.

6. CONCLUSION

This study aims to describe the characteristics of earnings management, financial constraints, environmental uncertainty, audit quality, and tax aggressiveness in mineral and coal mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2019–2023 period. Based on the results of descriptive statistical analysis of 95 observations from 19 sample companies, several important findings were obtained.

First, earnings management practices in mineral and coal mining companies in Indonesia are generally relatively low and show little variation between companies. This finding indicates that companies tend to present more stable and conservative financial statements, supported by high levels of oversight from regulators, investors, and other stakeholders.

Second, financial constraints vary significantly across companies. This reflects significant differences in access to funding, liquidity, and financial strength within the mining industry. Some companies have strong financial strength, while others face significant funding pressures due to the industry's capital-intensive nature and its strong influence on commodity price dynamics.

Third, the environmental uncertainty faced by companies is moderate and relatively consistent. Although the mining sector is highly vulnerable to changes in commodity prices, global geopolitical conditions, and changes in government regulations, most companies have

been able to adapt to the volatility of the business environment through various risk management strategies and long-term operational planning.

Fourth, tax aggressiveness shows a significant degree of variation across companies. This indicates that companies employ different tax management strategies according to their financial condition, operational characteristics, and management policies. These findings demonstrate that tax aggressiveness remains a relevant phenomenon in the mineral and coal mining sector in Indonesia.

Fifth, audit quality in the sample companies is considered high, as indicated by the predominant use of public accounting firms affiliated with the Big Four. This reflects growing corporate awareness of the importance of quality financial reporting, information transparency, and the implementation of good corporate governance as efforts to enhance corporate credibility in the eyes of investors and regulators.

Overall, this study shows that companies in the mineral and coal mining sector in Indonesia operate in a complex business environment characterized by funding pressures, market uncertainty, and demands for tax compliance and corporate governance. Despite relatively low earnings management practices and relatively good audit quality, significant differences remain between companies in the level of financial constraints and tax aggressiveness. These findings provide an empirical overview of the actual conditions of the Indonesian mining sector and provide an important basis for further research on the factors influencing tax aggressiveness and the effectiveness of corporate governance mechanisms in controlling opportunistic management behavior.

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